

Creating Science Gateway or HPC portal on OneSciencePlace

Duration: 90 mins

Recommended skill: Beginner

Requirements: Web browser

Project website: [OneSciencePlace.org](https://www.onescienceplace.org)

OneSciencePlace is a new platform to build an online and composable cyberinfrastructure that aims to transform delivery of FAIR content and computing in a single and easy to use environment. The platform could be used to build Science Gateways, HPC portals, Data repositories, Knowledgebase, and other highly customized applications. OneSciencePlace platform is built on a set of mature technologies that includes Drupal, SeedMeLab, Tapis and others. It can seamlessly interface with more than one compute resources such as Linux hosts, HPC clusters as well as data resources such as POSIX file systems or S3 object storage. Integration with other options such as Kubernetes and Globus are also on the future development roadmap.

This tutorial will focus on Science Gateway and HPC portal use cases and will guide attendees to explore OneSciencePlace in a hands-on manner. Each of the following aspects will be discussed/demonstrated in the tutorial with hands on component:

- Overview of available compute and data systems
- Using predefined applications (apps) (Hands-on)
 - o Containerized web app such as Jupyter/RStudio
 - o Containerized VNC app such as Linux Desktop
 - o Command line executable on a system
- Use above apps on a Linux host or an HPC cluster (Hands-on)
- Creating and using a apps along with their user interface (Hands-on)
- Adding a new compute system
- Authentication options including local accounts, LDAP or Single-sign-on
- FAIR publishing and data sharing

Attendee outcomes

Attendees will be able to gain hands-on experience of OneSciencePlace. They will learn to use apps and data management on more than one system, in a single environment. Attendees will gain an understanding of creating new apps along with its user interface with no-code. The tutorial will help germinate ideas on how OneSciencePlace could be used to serve as a single environment that seamlessly integrates to more than one cluster/host and provides users an ability to run a variety of applications. They will also gain an understanding and feasibility allowing users to bring and add their own applications on OneSciencePlace that is scalable and empowering to users.